

CAUSES, SYMPTOMS, APPEARANCE, TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEINS

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Abstract. In this article, we will discuss with you the uncomfortable disease of the legs, such as varicose veins, as well as the causes, symptoms, and treatment of varicose veins using traditional and folk medicine methods.

Keywords: Varicose causes, Varicose symptoms and signs, Varicose complications, Varicose diagnosis, Varicose treatment, Varicose prevention.

ПРИЧИНЫ, СИМПТОМЫ, ПОЯВЛЕНИЕ, ЛЕЧЕНИЕ ВАРИКОЗА

Аннотация. В этой статье мы обсудим с вами такое неприятное заболевание ног, как варикоз, а также причины, симптомы и лечение варикоза методами традиционной и народной медицины.

Ключевые слова: причины варикоза, симптомы и признаки варикоза, осложнения варикоза, диагностика варикоза, лечение варикоза, профилактика варикоза.

INTRODUCTION

What is varicose veins for the common man? Fatigue, swelling, bluish, sometimes dark veins in the legs. What is this disease from a medical point of view?

Varicose veins (varicose veins) are the enlargement and stretching of the veins (blood vessels that carry blood to the heart), usually in the legs, by thinning and forming knots. The nodules are formed as a result of the pathology of the venous walls and/or due to a genetic defect in their valves. Varicose veins in men and varicose veins in women are similar.

Dilation (enlargement) of veins occurs with an increase in venous pressure.

Varicose veins occur in the following places:

1. At the bottom of the legs;
2. In the stomach and esophagus;
3. In the small pelvis;
4. In the testicles and seminal vesicles.
5. The article discusses the most common place of the disease - varicose veins in the legs.
6. Varicose veins is one of the most common diseases today, it is registered in every third woman and every tenth man. Statisticians say that this disease often occurs at the age of 30-40 years.

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

CAUSES OF VARICOSIS. MAIN CAUSES OF VARICOSIS DEVELOPMENT:

- A lifestyle or profession associated with heavy physical exercise, standing for a long time in one position (standing or sitting) or constant high temperature of the environment;

- A significant increase in body weight;
- Hereditary (genetic) predisposition;
- Hormonal effect (pregnancy and taking hormonal drugs).

SECONDARY CAUSES OF VARICOSIS DEVELOPMENT

Obstructions related to the passage of blood through the veins. Examples of such obstacles are thrombosis or tumors.

Stress and nervous disorders. They affect the state of the veins. There are nerve endings in the wall of blood vessels that maintain their tension (tone). If the pressure increases, various toxins and alcohol affect them, the veins lose their tone and expand.

Arterial-venous anastomoses. Such anastomoses can be formed due to pressure in the flow area of arterial blood cells.

Sports tension. The risk group includes people who like to lift weights such as barbells. If there is a tendency to varicose veins, it is forbidden to strain the legs with heavy physical exercises and to lift weights.

Inappropriate clothing and shoes. Too tight clothing, such as tight pants, can cause varicose veins. In addition, narrow and high-heeled shoes are also harmful. When choosing shoes, preference should be given to wide heels, the wider the heel, the less the load on the feet. Walking and balancing in thin and high heels (stilettos) puts a lot of strain on the legs and veins, if you add to that heavy shopping bags...

These factors lead to dilatation of vessels, increased venous pressure and violation of the normal functioning of venous valves. As a result, pathological blood circulation in the veins of the legs - reflux (flow of blood from the deep veins to the reverse surface veins). It is this disease that causes the disease to increase over time and the load on the venous system to increase many times.

The correct flow of blood in the veins of the legs from the bottom to the top is carried out by several factors: blood pressure in the arteries, movement in the blood vessels to prevent the reverse flow of blood, and the presence of valves. The inability of these valves to perform their functions causes a violation of the blood flow in the veins, which leads to excessive stretching of the veins.

Due to this, the blood flow becomes irregular, the blood begins to stop in the lower veins of the legs (especially in the subcutaneous veins), the pressure in them increases, the vein walls expand and become thinner.

SYMPTOMS AND SIGNS OF VARICOSIS

- Symptoms of varicose veins are directly related to its stage.
- **STAGES I AND II OF VARICOSIS**
- The appearance of venous patterns in the legs, calves and thighs;
- Feeling of heaviness and pressure in the legs;
- Cramps, especially at night;
- Swelling of the legs after work, at the end of the day;
- Moderate pains in the legs;
- Fatigue quickly.
- **VARICOSE VEINS IN STAGE III AND IV**
- Swellings;

- Vascular stars (telangiectasias);
- Various pains (throbbing, itching in muscles, pain when walking, pain along the vein, general pain and cramping pain in the legs);
- The appearance of long varicose veins on the surface of the skin of the calves and heels;
- Changes in the skin (drying of the skin and pigmentation occurs, the skin of the legs darkens and is covered with brown spots). In addition, a number of diseases can be added to these symptoms later: dermatitis, eczema and trophic diseases, the appearance of ulcers.
- Rare but common symptoms include bleeding from ruptured veins, often at night.

RESEARCH RESULTS

COMPLICATIONS OF VARICOSIS

- If there are symptoms such as fever or weakness in varicose veins, this indicates the complications of the disease.
- Complications of varicose veins may include:
 - Eczema;
 - Skin lesions;
 - Severe venous bleeding even in superficial injuries;
 - Thrombophlebitis;
 - Trophic ulcer;
 - Phlebothrombosis;
 - Bleeding from varicose veins.
- **VARICOSIS DIAGNOSIS**
- When symptoms of varicose veins are detected or to make a correct diagnosis, it is necessary to consult a phlebologist, neurologist, or surgeon.
- Diagnostic method of varicose veins: ultrasound examination (UTT) or phlebography.

TREATMENT OF VARICOSIS

- How to treat varicose veins? The doctor will answer this question after the diagnosis. After all, treatment of varicose veins gives a positive result only if a correct diagnosis is made.
- In turn, the attending physician can choose the following treatment methods:
 - Treatment of varicose veins with drugs (medication) (cream, ointment, tablets);
 - Complex treatments depending on the symptomatology and stage of the disease (listed in the article below);
 - Surgical treatment (removal of damaged vessels).

ANTI-VARICOSE REMEDIES

ANTI-VARICOSE CREAM AND OINTMENTS

- Such tools are used in the initial stages of the disease as a means of auxiliary treatment and prevention of its development. They help to:
 - Pain reduction;
 - Reduce swelling;
 - Improving the performance of the valve system;
 - Increase the tone of vascular walls;

- Restoration of normal blood circulation;
- Avoiding the development of complications.

Troxevazin. Contains troxerutin, an active substance that normalizes the blood circulation system. Eliminates inflammation, reduces the thinness of capillaries, has venotonic properties, eliminates edema.

Detralex. It reduces blood stagnation in the ovaries and improves lymph and fluid flow.

Routine. Vitamin P (rutin and other bioflavonoids) reduces swelling, reduces inflammation, strengthens blood vessels, relieves varicose veins and prevents the formation of venous ulcers.

Aestin. Contains horse chestnut seeds. It reduces vascular permeability and the number of stars, increases tone, reduces inflammation, edema, blood clotting and improves microcirculation.

Venoruton. It contains oxerutin, which restores the functioning of the circulatory system. Eliminates inflammation. It prevents the formation of blood clots.

ANTI VARICOSIS TABLETS

- Tablets are used as a part of complex treatment if the disease cannot be affected locally. They help to:
 - Improve the tone of blood vessels;
 - Eliminating the inflammatory process;
 - Acceleration of blood flow and lymphatic drainage;
 - Elimination of microcirculatory diseases.

DISCUSSION

Venus. Increases the tone of blood vessels, reduces elasticity, conductivity, capillary fragility, significantly reduces venous blood stagnation, inflammation, protects against free radicals that damage blood vessel walls.

Anvenol. Reduces vascular permeability, improves microcirculation, expands arterioles, increases tone of blood vessels, improves peripheral blood circulation.

Escusan. This drug has anti-inflammatory and tonic properties, increases the strength of the vessel wall, reduces capillary fragility, prevents swelling and blood stagnation, relieves fatigue, heaviness, tension, itching, promotes health in various organs and tissues. accelerates the drying process.

Venoruton 300. It reduces edema, relieves pain, has an anti-gravity effect and improves microcirculation, eliminates trophic diseases and wounds.

Angistaxis. It increases the elasticity of blood vessels, normalizes blood vessel permeability, prevents the formation of edema and reduces existing edema.

TREATMENT OF VARICOSIS

Endovasal laser coagulation. The doctor affects the damaged vein with a laser, and as a result, the asterisks disappear. It is performed under local anesthesia. After a few weeks, there will be no trace of the treatment on the skin. It is used to treat varicose veins in the early stages.

Sclerotherapy. Special substances are injected into the dysfunctional vein, they completely condense and seal the veins, the vascular activity stops and the blood begins to flow through healthy veins. This treatment is not suitable for everyone. It is determined only if the nodes are not too large.

Ozone therapy. Ozone is injected into a vein with a small needle and seals the vein. A few treatments are enough to achieve a noticeable result. It is used to destroy blood vessel asterisks.

Phlebectomy. Surgical intervention, damaged vessels are simply removed. You can go home the next day after the operation, but you need to wear special socks or an elastic bandage for at least a month.

In the treatment of varicose veins, it is recommended to use therapeutic physical education and therapeutic knitting.

Therapeutic exercises for varicose veins. It helps to lose weight in the legs, normalize blood circulation and eliminate stagnation of venous blood.

If your occupation is sedentary, try to walk every day. Cycling and swimming are also recommended. However, running can have a negative effect on the condition of the veins.

TREATMENT OF VARICOSIS USING FOLK MEDICINE

- Important! Consult your doctor before using folk remedies to treat varicose veins!
- TREATMENT OF VARICOSE VEINS WITH HERBAL PREPARATIONS
- Here are a few benefits of herbal treatment:
- Phytotherapy eliminates the causes of the disease;
- Herbs have a minimal number of contraindications;
- Herbal treatment has very few side effects;
- Herbs, in addition to treating diseases, enrich tissues with vitamins and other nutrients;
- Prices are affordable.

Feathery kalanchoe. Kalanchoe leaves are thoroughly washed and put in a one-liter jar (the leaves should be half a jar). It is filled with 70% alcohol and stored in a dark place for 14 days. Shake (mix) well before use. Apply to your feet every day before going to bed. The pain goes away after the first application. If varicose veins are in the last stages, the treatment will last 4 months.

CONCLUSION

Apple "Antonovka". Put 3 apples in 1 liter of boiling water, close the lid and put it in a warm place for 4 hours. Then, without removing the apples, crush them, mix the solution and let it rest. Drink 50 g (about half a glass) with 1 tablespoon of honey in the morning and before going to bed in the evening. In addition, it cleans the blood, improves sleep and appetite.

Potatoes. Peel and grate 5 potatoes. Apply the resulting potato porridge on the feet. After 4 hours, the pain will disappear completely, and then wash the potatoes with warm water.

Garlic with oil. Take garlic and crush it. Mix with two parts butter. Before going to bed, apply it to the bulging veins and cover it with paper and tie it with a bandage or scarf. Wash in the morning and put warm and soft clothes on your feet.

PREVENTION OF VARICOSIS

- Prevention is better than cure. Consider some life rules that can prevent the appearance of varicose veins:
- If your job is sedentary, take a break from time to time. You can do special gymnastics at work. Try to walk more;
- If your job requires you to stand more, instead, take time to rest;
- Get rid of the habit of crossing one leg over the other when sitting, if you have one;
- Do not wear tight and constricting clothes (for example, tight jeans, it is strictly forbidden for women to wear tight clothes, in this case blood circulation in the area of the urogenital system is disturbed);

- Do not constantly wear shoes with high and thin heels (such shoes are rarely worn - on holidays);
- If you are constipated, don't let it go; constipation increases pelvic blood pressure;
- Ride a bike;
- Try to swim more;
- During rest, periodically place your leg higher (15-20 cm above the heart);
- Try to do regular exercise;
- Watch your weight;
- Reduce the consumption of harmful food and sweets, try to eat more fruits and vegetables, they are products rich in vitamins;
- Give up bad habits (smoking and drinking alcohol);
- Try taking a contrast shower (hot then cold and reverse);
- Drink at least 2 liters of water a day to prevent dehydration;
- Do not overdo it in the sun.

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